

EXAMINING THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF CORRUPTION: ARE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE CLEANEST AND MOST CORRUPT COUNTRIES BEFORE AND DURING COVID-19?

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ABSTRAK

Relevansi penelitian ini bermula dari kebutuhan untuk memahami dampak korupsi terhadap pertumbuhan ekonomi di berbagai kelompok negara, terutama sebelum dan selama pandemi COVID-19. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis apakah terdapat perbedaan dampak korupsi terhadap pertumbuhan ekonomi antara negara dengan tingkat korupsi terendah dan tertinggi, baik sebelum maupun selama pandemi. Dengan menggunakan analisis regresi data panel dengan model efek tetap dari tahun 2012 hingga 2020 dan mencakup 159 negara, penelitian ini mendukung teori "sand the wheels", yaitu korupsi menghambat pertumbuhan ekonomi. Tidak ditemukan perbedaan signifikan dalam pengaruh korupsi terhadap pertumbuhan ekonomi antara negara dengan indeks persepsi korupsi tinggi dan rendah, sebelum dan selama pandemi COVID-19. Selain itu, belanja per kapita dan kualitas regulasi berpengaruh positif terhadap pertumbuhan ekonomi. Di sisi lain, penanaman modal asing (FDI) dan keterbukaan perdagangan memiliki dampak yang berbeda di berbagai kelompok negara dan periode. Untuk mengurangi dampak buruk korupsi, kebijakan antikorupsi yang ketat sangat diperlukan untuk menciptakan lingkungan yang kondusif bagi pembangunan ekonomi berkelanjutan.

Kata kunci: COVID-19, korupsi, sand the wheels, regulasi, pertumbuhan ekonomi.

ABSTRACT

The relevance of this study stems from the need to understand the impact of corruption on economic growth across various groups of countries, particularly before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study aims to analyze whether there are differences in the impact of corruption on economic growth between countries with the lowest and highest levels of corruption, both before and during the pandemic. Using panel data regression analysis with a fixed-effects model from 2012 to 2020 and covering 159 countries, the study supports the "sand the wheels" theory, which suggests that corruption hinders economic growth. No significant differences were found in the effect of corruption on economic growth between countries with high and low corruption perception indices, both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, per capita spending and the quality of regulation positively impact economic growth. On the other hand, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and trade openness have varying effects on economic growth across different groups of countries and periods. To mitigate the negative impact of corruption, stringent anti-corruption policies create an environment conducive to sustainable economic development.

Key words: COVID-19, corruption, and the wheels, regulation, economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization can potentially bring significant benefits to both developing and developed countries. It is expected to improve living standards worldwide by enabling poorer countries to access foreign markets to sell goods, receive foreign investments, and open borders for education, employment, and remittances to support families and fund new businesses (Ayenagbo, 2021; Huda, 2024; Khoroshun et al., 2023; Stiglitz, 2007). Efforts to achieve higher economic growth are pursued through foreign trade, investment, industrialization, and urbanization (Shahbaz et al., 2018). Furthermore, globalization plays a crucial role in promoting sustainable development goals in developing countries through global trade in environmental goods and reducing carbon emissions across regions (Agusalim and Karim, 2023, 2024a, 2024b; P. Wang et al., 2024; Xiaoman et al., 2021). Increased economic integration through cross-border trade, capital flows, and technology dissemination is a hallmark of economic globalization (Agusalim and Pohan, 2017, 2018; Pratiwi and Wulansari, 2022; Rehman et al., 2021).

Globalization also induces structural changes in the modern world, affecting adjustments in national governance systems, economic changes, and political development strategies and creating sustainable global interdependence (Palley, 2021; Rode and Sáenz De Viteri, 2018; Su et al., 2023). Economic globalization can enhance economic growth through trade and foreign investment. For instance, trade can promote environmentally friendly technologies and structural transformation, ultimately improving environmental aspects (Lele et al., 2021). On the one hand, connectivity between countries enhances technology transfers. On the other hand, the growth of export opportunities for commodities in the era of free trade increases the production of goods with environmental costs through scale effects (Ahmed et al., 2019).

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic caused worldwide deglobalization and triggered global restrictions owing to its high spread rate. As of March 2022, there have been 6.69 million deaths and 664 million cases. The United States had the highest number of cases, with 79.6 million infections and 970,000 deaths, followed by India with 43 million infections and 517,000 deaths, Brazil with 29.7 million infections and 658,000 deaths, France with 23.8 million infections and 138,000 deaths, and the United Kingdom with 20.6 million infections and 164,000 deaths (Worldometers, 2022). COVID-19 has impacted the health sector and the economy (Agusalim et al., 2023, 2024; Sulistiyowati and Agusalim, 2023). The pandemic disrupted the manufacturing sector owing to restrictions leading to labor reductions, supply chain and transportation disruptions, and decreased demand (Baldwin and Weder, 2020). Surico and Galeotti (2020) and Gupta et al., (2021) viewed COVID-19 restrictions as causing income flow reductions as barriers to human movement and economic activities led to decreased economic activity and a decline in Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Figure 1 illustrates global trends in GDP per capita and economic growth from 2012 to 2020. Based on 2015 constant prices, GDP per capita increased yearly, reaching a peak of US\$11,012.4 in 2019. However, the COVID-19 pandemic caused a sharp decline in 2020 to US\$10,542.3, a decrease of US\$470.1 compared to the previous year. While economic growth remained stable in the years prior, it turned negative in 2020 due to the pandemic's impact. This sudden downturn represents one of the most significant global economic shocks in recent history. These data highlight how COVID-19 disrupted the previously stable and positive growth trends globally.

Figure 1

Global Trends in GDP per Capita and Economic Growth

Sources: World Bank, 2012-2020 (processed).

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a global economic recession, and corruption remains a significant global issue. Corrupt behavior is driven more by fear of punishment and inconvenience than moral values (Avritzer and Rennó, 2021; Denisova-Schmidt, 2020). Corruption, characterized by the misuse of power for personal gain, impedes economic development in developed and developing countries. Corruption is estimated to result in substantial economic losses, with more than US\$10 trillion lost annually, equivalent to 5 percent of the world's GDP. In response to the challenges of corruption, many countries have begun prioritizing anti-corruption efforts by establishing organizations, such as transparency international, to monitor and combat corruption.

The impact of corruption extends beyond economic implications and affects various sectors, such as politics, governance, and public trust. Corruption undermines the effectiveness of key institutions, such as the judiciary, military, and public service providers, leading to social issues such as poverty, disciplinary violations, and a culture of distrust. Additionally, corruption tends to exacerbate the political effects of recessions, with periods preceding deep crises often marked by a surge in corrupt practices. The link between corruption and

economic decline can worsen the challenges faced by society, further eroding trust in institutions and hindering overall development (Torcal and Christmann, 2021). The decline in political trust due to corruption incidents and the insensitivity of the political system persisted even after the economic recession, demonstrating the long-term impact of corruption on public trust.

Several studies have identified corruption as a significant obstacle to economic development in various countries. Desweni (2017) highlighted that corruption challenges the economic progress of both developed and developing countries. Wang (2016) and Deyshappriya (2015) found that corruption negatively affects economic growth, with specific evidence from China and general observations about economic growth barriers. This sentiment is also reflected in d'Agostino et al., (2016) for Africa and Tsanana et al., (2016) for European countries, where corruption has been shown to hinder GDP per capita growth. These studies suggest that corruption adversely affects economic growth.

On the flip side, however, some studies show that corruption positively affects economic growth. De Vaal and Ebben (2011) argued that corruption may positively affect economic growth in countries with under-developed institutions. Campbell

(2013) analyzed a sample of ten randomly chosen countries and found a similar relationship. Huang (2016) also found a unique case in South Korea where corruption was associated with increased economic growth. Saha et al., (2017) and Trabelsi (2024) argue that the relationship between corruption and economic growth is non-linear, with the former positively affecting the latter somewhat. These studies show that the link between corruption and economic growth is complex and determined by many factors and contexts.

The complexity of the impact of corruption on economic growth is evident in various studies. Akrouf (2020) emphasized the direct negative influence of corruption on economic growth and its indirect effects through factors such as investment, taxation, and public spending efficiency. Similarly, Grandes and Coremberg (2020) empirically demonstrate the macroeconomic costs of corruption on economic activity and growth. Moiseev et al., (2020) further explain that the effects of corruption on economic growth vary based on a country's economic conditions, slowing growth in developing countries but potentially enhancing it in East Asian economies.

Addressing corruption to improve economic performance requires institutional reforms. Pavlik et al., (2023) state that, despite recognizing corruption as a barrier to economic development, anticorruption reforms rarely last long. Akrouf et al., (2021) advocate institutional reforms to enhance governance quality as a prerequisite for sustainable economic growth. These findings align with the view that corruption undermines long-term economic performance and requires targeted policies to reduce it (Amoh et al., 2022). Transparency International is a renowned organization that annually releases the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) to assess perceived levels of corruption in countries worldwide. The CPI ranks countries on a scale from 0 to 100, where 0

indicates a very high level of corruption, and 100 indicates an immaculate country (Transparency International, 2021, 2022). The CPI is often used in academic research to measure corruption (John et al., 2023). In the 2020 CPI report, New Zealand and Denmark were identified as the cleanest countries, with 88 points each, followed by Finland, Singapore, and Sweden, with 85. Conversely, countries with the highest levels of corruption included Somalia and South Sudan, each scoring 12; Syria, scoring 14; and Venezuela and Yemen, each scoring 15. Interestingly, two-thirds of the countries evaluated in the report scored below 50, indicating that more countries were corrupt than clean.

The CPI is a critical benchmark metric for understanding global corruption and is widely used to assess countries' efforts to combat corruption (Cifuentes-Faura, 2024). The index relies on expert evaluations and opinion surveys, providing valuable insights into perceived corruption levels in various countries' public sectors Szymanski et al., (2022). Additionally, the CPI is often combined with other indicators, such as the World Bank's governance indicators, to analyze the impact of corruption on various aspects, such as economic growth, institutional quality, and market performance.

This study identifies countries with a CPI score less than or equal to 50 as the most corrupt countries. Countries with scores greater than 50 are categorized as the cleanest. Figure 2 shows the relationship between CPI, GDP per capita, and economic growth (ln GDP per capita). This figure consists of four panels, each showing data for 2019 and 2020 in both GDP per capita and ln GDP per capita formats. This presentation aims to illustrate the consistency of the pattern between corruption levels and economic indicators before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 2

Indication of the Relationship between CPI, GDP per Capita and Economic Growth

Sources: World Bank and Transparency International, 2019-2020 (processed).

In 2019 and 2020, countries with high CPI scores, indicating low levels of corruption, tend to have higher GDP per capita and economic growth. It suggests that the COVID-19 pandemic did not alter the relationship between CPI, GDP per capita, and economic growth. The most corrupt countries have low GDP per capita and economic growth rates. For example, Burundi has a GDP per capita of \$278.32 with a CPI score of only 20, followed by the Central African Republic with a GDP per capita of \$364.08 and a CPI score of 24, and Madagascar with a GDP per capita of \$442.93 and a CPI score of 25. These most corrupt countries generally have a GDP per capita of less than \$40,000. Conversely, countries that are clean from corruption tend to have higher GDP per capita. For instance, Luxembourg has a GDP per capita of \$104,526 and a CPI score of 80, followed by Switzerland with a GDP per capita of \$85,682 and a CPI score of 85, Ireland with a GDP per capita of \$78,558.3 and a CPI score of 72, Norway with a GDP per capita of \$75,017.2, and a CPI score of 84, and the United States with a GDP per capita of \$58,559.7, and a CPI score of 67. Overall, figure 2 indicates a strong relationship between low levels of corruption and high GDP per capita and

economic growth, which remains consistent both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

If observed closely in Figure 2, the variation in GDP per capita has a smaller gap among countries with CPI scores above 50 than among those below 50. Countries with high CPI scores also tend to have a high GDP per capita. This association is exemplified by Luxembourg, which has a CPI of 80 and a GDP per capita of US\$104,529.34. Conversely, Burundi, with a CPI of 19, has a GDP per capita of only US\$270.69.

Referring to the previous discussion, the author is interested in further examining the impact of corruption on economic growth in both the most corrupt and cleanest countries before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study reveals whether there is a difference in the influence of corruption on economic growth between these two groups of countries and between the periods before and during the pandemic. This comparative analysis allows policymakers to adopt appropriate measures to address corruption and foster economic growth.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Corruption, as defined by Transparency International, involves abusing entrusted

power for personal gain, often through illegal means and exploitation of authority (Bowra et al., 2022; Kohler and Wright, 2020; Kuncoro et al., 2020, 2022, 2023). Transparency International uses the CPI, which ranks countries based on their perceived levels of corruption in the public sector, to measure corruption. It ranges from 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean). The CPI is a primary tool, transparency international, that assesses and ranks a country based on perceived corruption levels in its public sector (Cifuentes-Faura, 2024). This index serves as an important metric for understanding corruption's worldwide prevalence and impact. The components used to compile the CPI include (1) Prevalence, as evidenced by bribery or abuse of authority by national employees; (2) Accountability, which is related to public funding that can be held accountable; (3) Motivation, indicating the desire to engage in corruption; (4) Affected institutions, such as public service institutions trapped in corruption cases, including essential services, licensing, taxation, customs, credit, audit institutions, police, trade, military, executive, and legislative bodies; and (5) Effectiveness, which refers to national employees' efforts to anticipate and tackle corruption (Ejiogu et al., 2021).

Grease the Wheels versus Sand the Wheels

The debate over whether corruption acts as a grease on the wheels or sand the wheels in the machinery of economic growth has been a compelling and contested topic in economic literature. The origins of this debate can be traced back to scholars such as Leff (1964), who introduced the concept of corruption as a means to spur economic growth through tips and bribes, known as the "grease the wheels hypothesis." On the other hand, the opposing view, which argues that corruption hinders economic development by creating inefficiencies and distorting market mechanisms, also emerged early, as seen in the works of Hall and Jones (1999) and Shleifer and Vishny (1993).

Research supporting the "grease the wheels" theory emphasizes the potential positive effects of corruption on economic growth. Lui (1985) suggests that corruption can efficiently reduce the time spent in administrative queues. Bribes can incentivize bureaucrats to expedite slow administration processes. Huntington (2006) argued that corruption helped overcome strict bureaucratic regulations and promoted growth, a phenomenon observed as early as 1870. By 1880, corruption involving railroad companies, utilities, and industries in the United States had resulted in faster growth. Studies such as those by Hussain et al., (2021) find that corruption can enhance economic growth by reducing bureaucratic obstacles and facilitating transactions, thus acting as a lubricant for the economy. Furthermore, some experts argue that corruption can shield poor policies in environments with weak governance institutions, ultimately boosting economic development (Dankumo et al., 2020).

Corruption is also believed to assist new businesses in navigating bureaucratic obstacles (Mendoza et al., 2015). Inefficient bureaucratic procedures can be circumvented through corrupt practices of private companies with officials (Habibov et al., 2017). Bologna and Ross (2015) suggest that corruption can help companies overcome regulatory burdens, protect value against capricious bureaucrats, reduce business risks, and promote innovation. According to Son et al., (2020), corruption can mitigate the negative impact of government regulations on entrepreneurship, thereby allowing businesses to operate efficiently.

Conversely, research supporting the "sand the wheels" theory emphasizes the detrimental effects of corruption on economic growth. Kurer (1993) argues that corruption acts as sand in the wheels of development, as corrupt officials have incentives to create additional distortions in the economy to maintain their sources of illicit income. Bardhan (1997) posits that the inherent uncertainty in corrupt activities

renders efficiency-enhancing mechanisms ineffective. Researchers, such as Zander (2021), note that corruption can lead to suboptimal economic outcomes by increasing transaction costs, distorting resource allocation, and increasing uncertainty. Additionally, studies indicate that corruption can hinder entrepreneurship, reduce business development, create barriers to market entry, and ultimately stifle economic progress (Hoinaru et al., 2020). Kéita and Laurila (2021) explain that corruption can reduce a company's productivity and negatively impact economic growth. Mauro et al., (2019) reveal that corruption can diminish government tax revenues, as many government officials siphon off the tax revenues paid by citizens. Corruption exacerbates national debt because corrupt officials fail to recognize the detrimental effects of their actions on public finances (Shittu et al., 2018). Zakharov (2019) states that corruption can deter investment, making investors wary of investing their money and thus hindering economic growth.

The debate between these two theories is ongoing and multifaceted. While some researchers argue that corruption can positively impact innovation and firm performance, others warn of its adverse effects on economic parameters (Iorio and Segnana, 2022). Recent research has investigated the varying relationship between corruption and economic growth by considering factors such as the level of tolerance for corruption and the threshold at which corruption becomes harmful to the economy (Saha et al., 2017; Trabelsi, 2024). This complexity is further compounded by the diverse impacts of corruption across different sectors, where corruption is known to have both positive and negative effects, as in the natural resources industry (Urbina and Rodríguez, 2022).

Empirical research has identified various factors influencing corruption and its impact on economic growth. According to Park (2012), burdensome government policies for private companies encourage bribery

to circumvent these policies. Lalountas et al., (2011) assert that low salaries for government employees drive them to abuse their power for additional income through corruption. Owoye (2017) explains that price controls invite mafias to bribe officials to sell goods at the desired price. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Goel (2021) found that government subsidies were often corrupt, resulting in misallocation of aid. Farzanegan and Hofmann (2021) added that vaccination processes could prompt bribery among officials to bypass registration procedures.

Corruption's impact on economic growth is diverse and multifaceted. Jahanzeb and Aziz (2017) demonstrate that corruption hampers economic growth. Hoinaru et al., (2020) also found that increasing corruption reduces government revenue and hinders economic growth. Similarly, Nur-begim and Jakee (2020) show that bribery to avoid bureaucratic requirements does not enhance productivity, thus negatively affecting firm performance. On the other hand, Goedhuys et al., (2016) show that corruption can expedite bureaucratic processes and stimulate economic growth. Supporting this view, Kim et al., (2017) suggest that corruption can attract investment by accelerating bureaucracy. Huang and Yuan (2021) argued that corruption can drive innovation while strong political institutions positively influence economic development.

Expanding on these findings, Sharma and Mitra (2015), using the generalized method of moments (GMM) method in several countries, found that high corruption and resource abundance significantly negatively impact economic growth. In contrast, the quality of human resources has a positive effect. In South Africa, Olamide and Maredza (2023) used correlation tests. They found that corruption and inflation have significant adverse effects on economic growth, investment has a positive impact, and foreign debt has a negative effect. In European countries using ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, Borlea et al., (2017) find that corruption affects the shadow

economy positively and negatively affects economic growth. Afonso and De Sá Fortes Leitão Rodrigues (2022), using various models in countries surveyed by Transparency International, found that corruption significantly negatively affects GDP per capita and private investment. Similarly, Obamuyi and Olayiwola (2019), using OLS regression in India and Nigeria, found that corruption significantly negatively affected economic growth, except when human capital, political instability, and capital formation were included in India.

Further supporting these findings, Awan et al., (2018), using a Fixed Effects Model (FEM) in South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries, found that government effectiveness and political stability significantly positively impacted economic growth, whereas corruption had a negative effect. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model in Latin America and the Caribbean, Useche and Reyes (2020) found that competitiveness positively impacts economic growth. In contrast, corruption significantly

negatively affects domestic and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and real GDP. Using the ARDL model in Peru, Marro et al., (2021) found that corruption negatively impacts GDP, with trade openness and political stability as control variables.

In line with these observations, Trabelsi (2024), using OLS and GMM in several countries, found that corruption negatively affects economic growth, with inflation having a negative effect. In contrast, investment and trade openness have positive impacts. Nguedie (2018), using Panel Smooth Transition Regression (PSTR) of developing countries, found that controlling corruption and investment positively impacts economic growth, with inflation having a negative effect, while investment, government consumption, and trade openness have positive impacts. Saha and Sen (2021), using Two-Stage Least Squares (TSLS), OLS, and GMM, found that corruption negatively affects GDP, democracy, education, and money supply, while openness has a positive impact.

Table 1
Research Variabl

No	Variable	Description
1	<i>growth</i>	GDP per capita (constant 2015 US\$) transformed into natural logarithm form used as an indicator of economic growth
2	<i>cpi</i>	CPI used as a measure of corruption obtained from Transparency International (0-100)
3	<i>ge_c</i>	General government final consumption expenditure (constant 2015 US\$) per capita (US\$)
4	<i>fdi_c</i>	FDI per capita. FDI includes equity capital, reinvested earnings, other long-term capital, and short-term capital divided by population. (Thousand US\$)
5	<i>to</i>	Trade openness. (exports + imports) / GDP *100 (Percent)
6	<i>rq</i>	Regulatory quality captures perceptions of the ability of the government to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations that permit and promote private sector development (-2.5 to 2.5)
7	<i>dc</i>	Dummy for COVID-19. Pre-COVID-19 = 0, During COVID-19 = 1
8	<i>dn</i>	Dummy for the country. Cleanest country = 1, Most corrupt country = 0

Source: diolah penulis (2024).

Building on the broader context of the impact of corruption during global crises, Attila (2020), using OLS in several countries, found that corruption and COVID-19 negatively impacted GDP per capita. In contrast, globalization and international trade had a positive impact. Finally, Inegbedion (2021), using TSLS and OLS in Nigeria, found that COVID-19-related restrictions significantly negatively impacted economic growth, reinforcing the broader negative implications of corruption during crisis periods.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study used secondary data from Transparency International and World Bank publications. The research period spans 2012 to 2020 and includes data from 159 countries surveyed by Transparency International. The literature review was based on international journals, books, and other scholarly literature. The variables used in this study were adapted and modified from the research conducted by Sharma and Mitra (2015) and are presented in table 1.

This study employs panel data regression analysis, a method used for empirical analysis with more dynamic data. Panel data combines cross-sectional and time-series data. Generally, a panel-data model can be expressed as follows:

$y_{it} = \alpha + \beta x_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$
 where $i = 1, \dots, N$ (cross section) and $t = 1, \dots, T$ (time series dimension). Parameter estimation in a panel data model can be conducted using techniques such as Pooled Least Squares (PLS), FEM, and the Random Effects Model (REM) (Gujarati, 2021). Three tests must be performed to determine the appropriate analytical technique for the panel data regression. The first test is the Chow Test, which is used to determine the difference between PLS and FEM techniques. The decision to use FEM is made if the Chow Test results show a cross-section F probability value less than the confidence level. Next, the Hausman Test was conducted to choose between FEM and REM. The decision to use FEM or REM was based on the chi-

squared (Chi²) probability value. If the Chi² probability is less than the confidence level, FEM is used; if it is greater, REM is used. Finally, a Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test was performed to choose between REM and PLS. If the LM value exceeds the Chi² table value, REM is used; otherwise, PLS is used (Agusalim et al., 2022).

The model specification used in this study is given in equation (2). This model determines whether corruption has a differential impact on economic growth in the cleanest and most corrupt countries before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The variables for CPI and government expenditure per capita are transformed into natural logarithmic forms. Meanwhile, the FDI and regulatory quality variables are not transformed because they contain negative values.

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_2 lcp_{it} dn_{it} + \beta_3 lcp_{it} dc_{it} + \beta_4 lge_{-c_{it}} + \beta_5 lge_{-c_{it}} dn_{it} + \beta_6 lge_{-c_{it}} dc_{it} + \beta_7 fdi_{-c_{it}} + \beta_8 fdi_{-c_{it}} dn_{it} + \beta_9 fdi_{-c_{it}} dc_{it} + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{11} to_{it} dn_{it} + \beta_{12} to_{it} dc_{it} + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \beta_{14} rq_{it} dn_{it} + \beta_{15} rq_{it} dc_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

For a more in-depth analysis, Eq. (2) can be rewritten into several equations as follows:

The cleanest countries (before the COVID-19 pandemic)

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_2 lcp_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_3 lcp_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_4 lge_{-c_{it}} + \beta_5 lge_{-c_{it}} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_6 lge_{-c_{it}} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_7 fdi_{c_{it}} + \beta_8 fdi_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_9 fdi_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{11} to_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_{12} to_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \beta_{14} rq_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_{15} rq_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + (\beta_1 + \beta_2) lcp_{it} + (\beta_4 + \beta_5) lge_{c_{it}} + (\beta_7 + \beta_8) fdi_{c_{it}} + (\beta_{10} + \beta_{11}) to_{it} + (\beta_{13} + \beta_{14}) rq_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

The significance of coefficients $\beta_2, \beta_5, \beta_8, \beta_{11}$, and β_{14} determines whether there are differences in the impact of the independent variables on economic growth

before the COVID-19 pandemic in the cleanest and most corrupt countries.

The cleanest countries (during the COVID-19 pandemic)

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_2 lcp_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_3 lcp_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_4 lge_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_5 lge_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_6 lge_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_7 fdi_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_8 fdi_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_9 fdi_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{11} to_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_{12} to_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \\
 & \beta_{14} rq_{it} dn_{it}(1) + \beta_{15} rq_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + (\beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3) lcp_{it} + (\beta_4 + \beta_5 + \beta_6) lge_{c_{it}} + (\beta_7 + \beta_8 + \beta_9) fdi_{c_{it}} + \\
 & (\beta_{10} + \beta_{11} + \beta_{12}) to_{it} + (\beta_{13} + \beta_{14} + \beta_{15}) rq_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

The significance of coefficients $\beta_3, \beta_6, \beta_9, \beta_{12}$, and β_{15} determines whether there are differences in the impact of the independent variables on economic growth before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The significance of the coefficients $\beta_2, \beta_5, \beta_8, \beta_{11}$, and β_{14} determines whether there are differences in the impact of the independent variables on economic growth in the cleanest and most corrupt countries.

The most corrupt countries (before the COVID-19 pandemic)

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_2 lcp_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_3 lcp_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_4 lge_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_5 lge_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_6 lge_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_7 fdi_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_8 fdi_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_9 fdi_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{11} to_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_{12} to_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \\
 & \beta_{14} rq_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_{15} rq_{it} dc_{it}(0) + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_4 lge_{c_{it}} + \beta_7 fdi_{c_{it}} + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

The significance of coefficients $\beta_1, \beta_4, \beta_7, \beta_{10}$, and β_{13} determines whether the independent variables have an impact on

economic growth in the most corrupt countries before the COVID-19 pandemic.

The most corrupt countries (during the COVID-19 pandemic)

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 lcp_{it} + \beta_2 lcp_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_3 lcp_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_4 lge_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_5 lge_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_6 lge_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_7 fdi_{c_{it}} + \\
 & \beta_8 fdi_{c_{it}} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_9 fdi_{c_{it}} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_{10} to_{it} + \beta_{11} to_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_{12} to_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \beta_{13} rq_{it} + \\
 & \beta_{14} rq_{it} dn_{it}(0) + \beta_{15} rq_{it} dc_{it}(1) + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 growth_{it} = & \alpha + (\beta_1 + \beta_3) lcp_{it} + (\beta_4 + \beta_6) lge_{c_{it}} + (\beta_7 + \beta_9) fdi_{c_{it}} + (\beta_{10} + \beta_{12}) to_{it} + (\beta_{13} + \beta_{15}) rq_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

The significance of the coefficients $\beta_3, \beta_6, \beta_9, \beta_{12}$, and β_{15} determines whether there are differences in the impact of the independent variables on economic growth before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the most corrupt countries.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents a descriptive analysis, examines the impact of corruption on economic growth, and provides examples of policies for preventing and addressing corruption based on the success stories of the world's cleanest countries.

The analysis begins by providing an overview of CPI movement, economic growth, and GDP per capita before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Table 2 shows the economic performance of the ten countries with the lowest and highest levels of corruption before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Countries with high CPI scores, such as Denmark, New Zealand, and Finland, tend to have high GDP per capita despite relatively low economic growth rates. This phenomenon is due to the large scale of their economies and the optimal utilization of resources in these countries. For example, Luxembourg had a GDP per capita of US\$108,526 in 2019, with an eco-

economic growth rate of 3.28 percent, whereas its CPI was 80. Conversely, countries with low CPI scores, such as Somalia, Sudan, and Haiti, tend to have low GDP per capita, although there is considerable variation in their economic growth rates (Al Qudah et al., 2020; Christos et al., 2024; Verlanov, 2022). For instance, Somalia had a GDP per capita of \$446.85 in 2019, with an economic growth rate of 8.08 percent, whereas Sudan had a GDP per capita of \$1,198.52, with an economic growth rate of -2.18 percent. Table 2 also indicates that both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, there was no

significant change in CPI scores. However, most countries' GDP per capita and economic growth rates have declined.

Figure 3 illustrates GDP per capita trends and compares the cleanest and most corrupt countries over the past five years. The graph clearly shows no significant changes in GDP per capita in either the low- or high-corruption countries. However, there is a noticeable gap in GDP per capita between these two groups, with the GDP per capita of the cleanest countries being at least five times higher than that of the most corrupt countries.

Table 2
Economic Performance in the 10 Cleanest and Most Corrupt Countries (2019-2020)

Country	2019			2020		
	CPI	Growth (%)	GDP_C (US\$)	CPI	Growth (%)	GDP_C (US\$)
Cleanest Countries						
Denmark	87	2,11	57.553,11	88	-2,06	56.202,21
New Zealand	87	2,19	40.315,51	88	-1,25	40.218,42
Finland	86	1,22	46.116,53	85	-2,30	44.751,31
Singapore	85	1,10	61.173,91	85	-4,14	58.056,82
Sweden	85	1,99	53.490,41	85	-2,94	51.539,62
Switzerland	85	1,21	88.413,32	85	-2,39	85.413,22
Norway	84	0,75	76.005,23	84	-0,72	75.017,23
Netherlands	82	1,96	48.424,31	82	-3,80	46.327,71
Germany	80	1,06	43.311,62	80	-4,57	41.259,21
Luxembourg	80	3,28	108.526	80	-1,78	104.529
Most Corrupt Countries						
Somalia	9	8,08	446,85	12	2,44	444,79
Sudan	16	-2,18	1.198,52	16	-3,62	1.127,72
Haiti	18	-1,68	1.373,88	18	-3,34	1.311,71
Congo, Dem. Rep.	18	4,38	512,59	18	1,73	505,35
Burundi	19	1,81	278,32	19	0,32	270,69
Guinea-Bissau	19	4,50	650,70	19	-2,40	619,29
Cambodia	20	7,05	1.441,18	20	-3,10	1.376,41
Chad	20	3,25	660,07	20	-1,60	634,75
Comoros	25	1,76	1.284,29	21	-0,29	1.255,04
Nicaragua	22	-3,78	1.984,82	22	-1,79	1.922,35

Sources: World Bank and Transparency International, 2020 (processed)

Figure 3

GDP per Capita Trends and Comparison in the Cleanest and Most Corrupt Countries

Sources: World Bank and Transparency International, 2019-2020 (processed).

Figure 4

Economic Growth Trends in the Cleanest and Most Corrupt Countries

Sources: World Bank and Transparency International, 2019-2020 (processed).

This fact reflects that corruption-free countries can optimally utilize their resources, resulting in higher prosperity for their citizens (Kuipers and Verhey, 2023). Conversely, countries with high levels of corruption tend to experience inefficiencies in resource management, negatively impacting economic growth and prosperity (Trpeski et al., 2023). This relationship also indicates that corruption is one of the main obstacles to sustainable economic development (Orudzheva and Sluhan, 2023).

Figure 4 illustrates the trends in economic growth in the countries with the lowest and highest levels of corruption. Economic growth rates in the cleanest countries tend to be lower than those in the most corrupt

countries. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, the economic growth in both groups of countries was relatively stable. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a sharp decline in the economic growth rates in both groups of countries. Although the most corrupt countries had higher economic growth before the pandemic, both groups felt that this had a negative impact on economic growth. Xiang et al., (2021) showed that the pandemic caused a sharp decline in economic growth rates worldwide, affecting various sectors and industries. The economic impact of the pandemic was widespread, affecting overall GDP growth and specific sectors, such as manufacturing, agriculture, and international trade (Arifah and Kim, 2022; Fauzan et al., 2024). Disruptions caused by the pandemic have highlighted vulnerabilities in global supply chains, financial markets, and government policies (Farida et al., 2023; Lazarov et al., 2023). This impact was particularly noticeable in countries heavily reliant on sectors susceptible to lockdowns and restrictions, such as tourism and hospitality (Antara and Sumarniasih, 2024).

The Effect of Corruption on Economics Growth

After conducting the Chow, Hausman, and Lagrange Multiplier (LM) tests, Table 4 indicates that the appropriate estimation method is FEM. The estimation results show an R-squared value of 0.6443, indicating that the regression model explains approximately 64.43 percent of the variation in economic growth. In other words, 64.4 percent of the changes in economic growth could be explained by changes in the independent variables included in the regression analysis. The remaining 35.57 percent is the variation not explained by the model and may be due to other factors not included. This R-squared value suggests that the model has a reasonably good ability to explain the data variability. An F-statistic value of 3.66, with a probability of less than 0.05, indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant. This test result indicates that the

CPI variable, together with other control variables, collectively has a significant influence on economic growth.

Table 4 has been reorganized into table 5 to facilitate a partial analysis of the impact of

the independent variables on economic growth. Table 5 compares the estimation results for the two groups of countries before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 4
Panel Data Regression Analysis Results

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Economic Growth (<i>lgdp_c</i>)
<i>cpi</i>	0.166*** (0.0498)
<i>lge_c</i>	0.00429*** (0.00164)
<i>fdi_c</i>	9.81e-08 (1.45e-07)
<i>to</i>	-0.000744* (0.000391)
<i>rq</i>	0.0473** (0.0223)
<i>lcpi * dn</i>	-0.0361 (0.144)
<i>lcpi * dc</i>	0.00763 (0.00807)
<i>lge_c * dn</i>	1.99e-11 (9.91e-09)
<i>lge_c * dc</i>	-0.00519 (0.00397)
<i>fdi_c * dn</i>	-2.08e-07 (2.70e-07)
<i>fdi_c * dc</i>	-3.45e-07* (1.89e-07)
<i>to * dn</i>	0.0012303* (0.000672)
<i>to * dc</i>	0.000110 (0.000211)
<i>rq * dn</i>	0.114** (0.0529)
<i>rq * dc</i>	0.0277** (0.0138)
<i>_cons</i>	8.037*** (0.228)
R-squared	0,6443
F-Statistic	3.66
Observations	1290
Countries	159
Best Model Selection	FEM
Chow Test	FEM
Hausman Test	FEM
LM Test	REM

Note: Standard errors are in parentheses; the significance levels are *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.1$.

Table 5
Estimation Results for Periods Pre- and During COVID-19 in the Cleanest and Most Corrupt Countries

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Economic Growth (<i>lgdp_c</i>)			
	Cleanest Countries		Most Corrupt Countries	
	Pre-COVID-19	During COVID-19	Pre-COVID-19	During COVID-19
<i>cpi</i>	0.166	0.166	0.166	0.166
<i>lge_c</i>	0.00429	0.00429	0.00429	0.00429
<i>fdi_c</i>	-	-3.45e-07	-	-3.45e-07
<i>to</i>	0.0004863	0.0004863	-0.000744	-0.000744
<i>rq</i>	0.1613	0.189	0.0473	0.075

Source: Author's calculations.

Based on the estimation results in tables 4 and 5, it can be demonstrated that CPI positively affects economic growth. In other words, the cleaner a country is from corruption, the higher its economic growth rate. Thus, corruption plays a crucial role in hindering economic growth. This finding supports the "sand the wheels" theory, which posits that corruption creates inefficiencies and distortions in market mechanisms, hindering economic development, as argued by Kurer (1993), Shleifer and Vishny (1993), Bardhan (1997), and Hall and Jones (1999). This argument contradicts the views of Leff (1964), Lui (1985), and Huntington (2006), who support the theory that corruption "greases the wheels."

Recent empirical studies also support these results. Trpeski et al., (2023) emphasize tackling corruption through effective policies and measures to ensure sustainable economic growth. Ibrahim (2021) supported this idea by highlighting how corruption increases business costs, reduces incentives, and hampers investment and economic growth. Vivien et al., (2023) further contribute to this understanding by showing the destructive impact of corruption on economic growth in Mali and stressing the importance of considering the threshold at which corruption begins to hinder economic development. Research by Kwadwo et al., (2020) found that corruption significantly impedes economic growth in Ghana.

Yahyaoui (2024) explores how corruption acts as a significant barrier to economic growth by affecting investment activities and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows, further reinforcing the negative impact of corruption on economic progress. The detrimental effects of corruption on economic growth are reiterated by Kuipers and Verhey (2023), who state that corruption is widely recognized as a significant obstacle to economic development. Amoh et al., (2022) provide new empirical evidence from developing countries, showing that corruption encompasses various activities that hinder economic growth. Rotimi et al., (2023) focused

on the dynamics of corruption in Nigeria and concluded that ongoing corruption impedes economic growth.

Bouteraa et al., (2024) present findings that corruption hampers economic growth by almost 19 percent, highlighting the significant negative impact of corruption on economic development. Akbar et al., (2020) provided evidence of the hindering effect of corruption on economic growth in ASEAN countries, further reinforcing the relationship between corruption and economic stagnation. Akrouf (2020) confirms a direct negative relationship between corruption and economic growth in Tunisia, emphasizing that increased levels of corruption lead to a decline in economic growth.

This study also found no difference in the impact of corruption on economic growth between the cleanest and most corrupt countries before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This finding indicates that corruption can hinder economic progress in developed and developing countries. Although corruption is generally believed to have a more significant negative impact on economic growth in countries with poor governance, recent research has shown that the influence of corruption on economic growth remains consistent in countries with different levels of perceived corruption.

Nasir et al., (2021) and Pham (2020) show the relationship between corruption and economic growth in various regions. Nasir et al., (2021) focus on ten Asia-Pacific countries and analyze the impact of corruption, FDI, population growth, and government expenditure on economic growth. On the other hand, Pham (2020) investigated the impact of corruption control on economic growth in developing countries, emphasizing the importance of enhancing anti-corruption measures to improve economic efficiency. Contrary to traditional assumptions, research by Bouteraa et al., (2024) shows that corruption can impede economic progress even in countries with relatively clean governance structures.

In addition to corruption, government expenditure per capita also significantly influences economic growth. An increase in per capita government expenditure leads to economic growth. This study found no difference in the impact between the cleanest and most corrupt countries before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Government spending is a crucial driver of economic growth in corrupt-free countries. For example, Trpeski et al., (2023) found that government spending positively and significantly impacts economic growth in Central and Eastern Europe. Research in Eurozone countries concludes that higher government spending can boost economic growth, especially in less-developed and poorer countries (Cenc, 2022).

Conversely, in highly corrupt countries, government spending still plays a vital role in stimulating economic growth despite the challenges posed by corruption. Mardiyani et al., (2023) conducted research in Indonesia, and Rosli and Kamaluddin (2021), in Southeast Asian countries, found that government expenditure can drive economic growth by increasing production capacity, creating jobs, and ultimately raising income levels, even amid corruption. Similar findings were reported by Saputro and Aisyah (2023) in lower-middle-income countries and by Wawrzyniak and Doryń (2020) in developing countries.

Moreover, FDI per capita significantly negatively impacts economic growth, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, in the cleanest and most corrupt countries. However, before the pandemic, FDI per capita had no significant effect on economic growth. This finding contradicts general knowledge, as FDI is typically considered an important factor in economic development and often catalyzes economic growth in many countries. This finding is similar to Eniekezimene et al.,'s (2024) study in Nigeria, in which FDI did not significantly impact economic growth. Anetor (2020) explains that the negative impact of FDI on economic growth is due to a sectoral bias in

investment allocation. In many countries, FDI inflows are often concentrated in the primary sector, neglecting other important economic sectors. This bias can limit the overall positive impact of FDI on economic growth, especially during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, a significant factor contributing to the negative impact of FDI on economic growth during the pandemic is the disruption of global supply chains owing to lockdowns and restrictions imposed to mitigate the spread of the virus. The COVID-19 crisis has caused widespread disruptions in global supply chains, affecting the production and distribution of goods and services.

Furthermore, trade openness has proven beneficial in driving economic growth, especially in countries with low levels of corruption. Trade openness hinders economic growth in countries with the lowest corruption levels, such as Denmark and New Zealand, significantly enhancing efficiency, innovation, and global competitiveness. Empirically, Denmark, with a high CPI score, maintained a high GDP per capita and sustained it at relatively high levels during the pandemic, mainly because trade openness drove economic stability. Alfano et al., (2021) indicated that corruption thrives due to economic rents, which diminish as trade openness increases. This relationship implies that countries with lower corruption levels, facilitated by open trade policies, are more likely to experience efficient resource allocation and economic development. Akinlo and Okunlola (2021) further support this notion by emphasizing that the interaction between trade openness and institutional quality can positively impact economic growth, highlighting the importance of clean governance structures in maximizing the benefits of trade openness. Similar findings were reported by Kong et al., (2021), who stated that higher economic openness helps boost economic growth through taxes and gains from exports and imports.

Conversely, despite attempts to implement economic openness, highly corrupt

countries, such as Somalia, struggle to utilize it optimally, as corruption hinders resource allocation and reduces investor confidence, reflected in a much lower and unstable GDP per capita. Therefore, the same level of economic openness can yield vastly different outcomes, depending on the country's corruption level. Bahoo et al., (2022) state that trade openness has a complex relationship with economic growth in corruption-affected countries. While trade openness is generally considered beneficial for economic development owing to increased market access, efficiency, and technology transfer, corruption can impede its impact. Corruption, characterized by dishonest or fraudulent conduct by those in power, can significantly hinder economic growth by distorting market mechanisms, reducing investor confidence, and diverting resources from productive use. Miah et al., (2021) stated that corruption negatively affects economic growth in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. Corruption can undermine the effectiveness of trade openness initiatives by increasing trade costs and creating an uncertain environment that hinders foreign investment and economic progress (Yu et al., 2023).

Finally, this study finds that regulatory quality is important in driving economic growth, particularly in countries with low levels of corruption. Regulatory quality drives economic progress by ensuring transparency, accountability, and efficiency in government and business operations. Upholding the rule of law and combating corruption, regulatory quality creates a fair business environment, reduces bureaucratic obstacles, and promotes economic growth (Galabada, 2021). The stable and predictable business environment created by high regulatory quality attracts investment, fosters innovation, and supports overall economic development (Yakubu, 2020). Moreover, regulatory quality is linked to improved governance, reduced corruption, and enhanced democracy, which is crucial for sustainable economic growth (Sukarno and

Nurmandi, 2023). These results are supported by other studies that show that efficient government regulation of resource management can boost economic growth (Murshed et al., (2021). Other studies, such as Tiwari and Bharadwaj (2021) and Elham (2020), confirm that government effectiveness, regulatory quality, and corruption control significantly impact economic growth.

Anti-corruption Policy

Anti-corruption policies are crucial for enforcing transparency, accountability, and integrity in global governance systems. International organizations typically advocate various anti-corruption measures to combat corrupt practices effectively. These measures include asset and interest declarations, beneficial ownership disclosure, transparency in political financing, whistleblowing mechanisms, transparency in lobbying activities, and promoting contract openness (Artello and Albanese, 2020; Atilas, 2024). In line with these international efforts, countries worldwide, regardless of their level of development, have recognized the importance of implementing anti-corruption policies to identify and punish individuals involved in corrupt activities. Establishing anti-corruption laws and actions significantly contributes to addressing corruption in a country (Brody et al., 2020; Bussmann et al., 2018).

Experts note the emergence of global anti-corruption norms, characterized by efforts to raise awareness about corruption issues, institutionalize anti-corruption commitments through legal and policy frameworks and ensure stakeholder acceptance of anti-corruption norms (Bowra et al., 2022). The effectiveness of anti-corruption programs often depends on integrating top-down and bottom-up approaches to address corruption comprehensively (Ulain and Hussain, 2020). The top-down approach involves policies and actions initiated by leaders and governments to eradicate corruption from the top levels. In contrast, the bottom-up approach involves the

participation of society and local stakeholders to create grassroots pressure and support to fight corruption. Combining these approaches ensures that anti-corruption efforts are comprehensive and encompass policy initiatives and public participation.

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic underscored the importance of strengthening anti-corruption efforts in healthcare systems by enhancing accountability and transparency. Research by (Gorodensky et al., 2022) indicates that international health organizations must improve these aspects to combat corruption effectively. The best practices in anti-corruption mechanisms include delivering quality healthcare services, aligning stakeholder incentives with health goals, and designing resilient systems (Wierzynska et al., 2020). By adopting these approaches, healthcare systems can become more robust, improve public trust, and enhance service effectiveness. The pandemic has highlighted that the integrity of healthcare systems is crucial for maintaining quality service delivery to the public.

Successful anti-corruption policies often require reviewing and implementing best practices to improve governance and combat corrupt behavior (Nonik et al., 2024). Countries that have successfully implemented anti-corruption policies can serve as valuable examples of others striving to fight corruption effectively. Research has highlighted the fact that several countries are excelling in this regard. For instance, European Union (EU) member states have demonstrated effective anti-corruption practices, positioning the EU as a leader in this field (Melnyk et al., 2022). Moreover, countries like New Zealand, Singapore, and Hong Kong have minimized corruption through strong leadership and cultural factors (Quah, 2022). Finland's approach integrates anti-corruption activities into national policies, emphasizing the importance of a holistic strategy (Lytvyn et al., 2023).

However, some countries have faced challenges in combating corruption. For example, Asian countries struggle because

they rely on corrupt political leaders and ineffective anti-corruption institutions (Quah, 2021). Additionally, post-Soviet countries, such as Ukraine, encounter obstacles in implementing national anti-corruption policies (Zakharova et al., 2021). Decentralization has been identified as a strategy that, if effectively implemented, can reduce corruption in specific environments (Walton, 2023).

Therefore, successful anti-corruption policies often involve leadership, culture, legal mechanisms, and public integrity. A nation can enhance its anti-corruption efforts by studying its best practices and adopting successful approaches from other countries. Freedom of the press is also crucial in enhancing public integrity and reducing corruption by ensuring transparency and accountability (Mutiah et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study focuses on the urgency of understanding the relationship between corruption and economic growth in the cleanest and most corrupt countries, particularly before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicate that countries with lower levels of corruption tend to experience higher economic growth. This finding supports the theory of 'sand the wheels,' which argues that corruption creates inefficiencies and distortions in market mechanisms, hindering economic development. Additionally, this study found no significant difference in the impact of corruption on economic growth between the cleanest and most corrupt countries, both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This finding suggests that the detrimental effects of corruption on the economy are universal and apply to both developed and developing countries. Although corruption is often believed to have a more significant impact on countries with weak governance, these findings indicate that the adverse effects of corruption on economic growth are consistent across countries with varying levels of corruption.

Based on the research findings, the CPI, government spending, trade openness, and regulatory quality contribute to economic growth. The following are some policy recommendations based on these findings. First, anti-corruption policies should focus on improving transparency and accountability within the government, including asset declarations, beneficial ownership disclosures, and transparency in political financing. Additionally, effective reporting mechanisms should be developed to detect and address corruption, involving the participation of society and local stakeholders in a comprehensive strategy. Second, governments should prioritize spending in sectors that promote high-quality economic growth, such as infrastructure, social services, and education and skills training. Investment in human capital is crucial to ensure that economic growth is high but sustainable and inclusive. Third, to support trade openness, national policies should focus on increasing transparency and reducing corruption so that the positive impacts of trade openness can be maximized, especially in countries with lower levels of corruption. Countries with higher levels of corruption should address the potential negative impacts of trade openness by adopting policies that improve governance and create a more stable and equitable business environment. Fourth, governments should implement regulatory reforms that streamline bureaucratic procedures, create a more transparent and efficient business climate, and support innovation and economic competitiveness to enhance regulatory quality. These policies are expected to foster more stable and high-quality economic growth and enhance nations' global competitiveness.

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